

Improving Students' Reading Competence through Independent Study

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the issues based on improving students' reading competence through independent study. As we know, independent work of students, included in the learning process, is work that is performed without the direct participation of the teacher, but according to his instructions at a time specially provided for this; at the same time, students consciously strive to achieve the goal set in the task, showing their efforts and expressing in one form or another the results of their mental and physical actions. In the course of researching the topic, the author analyzes the principles of independent work and reading strategies that will help improve reading competence.

Keywords: reading competence, independent study, learning process.

INTRODUCTION

Organizing and managing independent work is the responsible and difficult work of every teacher. When talking about developing independence in schoolchildren, it is necessary to keep in mind two closely related tasks. The first of them is to develop students' independence in cognitive activity, teach them to independently acquire knowledge, and form their own worldview; the second is to teach them to independently apply existing knowledge in learning and practical activities. Independent work is not an end in itself. It is a means of struggle for deep and lasting knowledge of students, a means of struggle for deep and lasting skills and abilities, a means of developing their activity and independence as personality traits, and developing their mental abilities.

When building a system of independent work, the following were put forward as the main didactic requirements:

1. The system of independent work should contribute to the solution of basic didactic tasks - the acquisition of deep and lasting knowledge by students, the development of their cognitive abilities, the formation of the ability to independently acquire, expand and deepen knowledge, and apply it in practice.

2. The system must satisfy the basic principles of didactics, and, above all, the principles of accessibility and systematicity, the connection of theory with practice, conscious and creative activity, and the principle of teaching at a high scientific level.

3. The work included in the system should be varied in educational purpose and content to ensure that students develop a variety of skills and abilities.

4. The sequence of performing homework and classroom independent work should logically follow from the previous ones and prepare the ground for performing subsequent ones. In this case, not only “short-range” but also “long-distance” connections are provided between individual jobs. The success of solving this problem depends not only on the pedagogical skill of the teacher, but also on how he understands the meaning and place of each individual work in the system of work, in the development of students’ cognitive abilities, their thinking and other qualities [4]

DISCUSSIONS

The effectiveness of independent work is achieved if it is one of the integral, organic elements of the educational process, and special time is provided for it in each lesson, if it is carried out systematically and systematically, and not randomly and episodically.

Reading as a complex speech activity is closely related to the characteristics of society; it is part of the individual’s culture and, even more so, cannot help but transform under the influence of changes affecting the information sphere of human life. Therefore, in this paragraph, devoted to the essence and characteristics of reading, our attention is primarily directed to the current state of the information

society, which gives rise to the development of a new type of personality that requires a revision of educational traditions, and contributes to the renewal of reading activities.

Practice shows that students have difficulty coping with large volumes of texts in their chosen educational programs, both general education and professional. Society needs specialists with a high level of professional competencies, and a competent specialist is considered to be one who is able to assimilate a large amount of information, accumulate it and actively apply it in professional activities.

Among the main tasks of developing reading competence of students of professional educational organizations are the following:

- development of communicative, intellectual and reflective abilities;
- enrichment of personal and professional experience;
- increasing adaptation to living conditions and activities in the information space.

Successful work on developing students' reading competence will ultimately allow the student, when working with text, to: analyze and assimilate information, generalize knowledge obtained not only from the content of the text, but also from his own experience, divide information into essential and non-essential. The formation of this competence will significantly increase the efficiency of the educational process, since it is aimed at working with a variety of sources of special information that students can use throughout not only the period of study, but also throughout their future professional activities.

Over the past decades, society has realized that lifelong education is of great future importance. This is due to the need to improve. Therefore, the ability to read is not only about mastering the reading technique acquired in elementary school. Now it is a constantly developing body of knowledge, skills and abilities, i.e.

competencies that are perfected by a person at different stages of activity and communication throughout life.

Reading competence is “a criterion for a high level of professional education” (T. A. Olkhovskaya) and is “an integrative characteristic of a competitive personality” (Ch. Edelhoff).

The study of modern psychological and pedagogical research indicates the presence of attempts to solve the issue of developing students' reading competence through the means of a foreign language. A whole series of studies have been carried out in the concept of a school of professionally oriented reading (T. G. Agapitova, E. G. Galizina, S. A. Zhukova, E. V. Krylova, M. A. Mosina, T. S. Serova, etc.), in which the functions, subject content of foreign language reading, psychological mechanisms, internal and external structure of professionally oriented reading are revealed, ways of a thesaurus-targeted approach to the selection and organization of the reader's vocabulary, and methods of teaching professionally oriented informative reading to specialists of various profiles are developed.

A number of scientists note that thanks to the existing experience in the native and first foreign languages, the formation of reading competence in classes in a second foreign language occurs in a much shorter time (3. I. Klychnikova, S. K. Folomkina, N. Willenberg, G. Westhoff and etc.).

While reading, students should be taught:

- read authentic texts of different genres and styles with an understanding of the main content;

- read authentic texts of different genres and styles with full and accurate understanding and using various techniques for semantic processing of texts (linguistic guesses, selective translation), as well as reference materials, be able to evaluate the information received, express your opinion;

-read authentic texts with a selective understanding of significant/necessary/interesting information; • read authentic texts with a selective understanding of significant/necessary/interesting information;

Reading and understanding of texts with varying depth of penetration into their content depending on the type of reading: with understanding of the main content (introductory reading), with full understanding (study reading), with selective understanding of the necessary or interesting information (scanning reading). Even at the final stage of learning, expressive reading aloud returns again as a special type of reading and a subject of control. Regardless of the type of reading, it is possible to use a bilingual and/or monolingual explanatory dictionary.

ANALYSIS

Reading with an understanding of the main content of the text (introductory reading) is carried out using authentic materials. Introductory reading strategies include the formation of the following skills:-

-visually perceive the text, recognize familiar words and grammatical phenomena and understand the main content of authentic texts of different genres and styles

- determine the topic, the main content of the text by the title, selective reading of text fragments;

- highlight semantic milestones, the main idea of the text;

-break the text into relatively independent semantic parts;

-title the text and its individual parts;

- select the main facts from the text, omitting the secondary ones;

- establish a logical sequence of the main facts of the text;

- identify cause-and-effect relationships in the text;

- present the content of the text briefly and logically;

- evaluate what you read, compare facts within different cultures.

- predict the content of the text based on the title or beginning of the text;

-guess the meaning of unfamiliar words based on their similarity to the Russian language, word-formation elements, and context;

-ignore unfamiliar words that do not interfere with understanding the main content of the text.

Reading with a full understanding of the text (study reading) is carried out on authentic materials, pragmatic texts, focused on the substantive content of speech at each stage.

Strategies for learning to read involve the formation of such skills as

- fully and accurately understand the content of the text based on linguistic and contextual guesses, word-formation analysis, using mainly the English-Russian dictionary and master the techniques of searching for words in explanatory dictionaries;

- briefly and/or detail the content of what you read;

- interpret what you read - express your opinion, relate it to your experience, fully and accurately understanding the text based on its information processing.

-analyze the structure and meaning of individual parts of the text, taking into account differences in the structures of the native and studied languages. translate individual text fragments;

-establish a cause-and-effect relationship between facts and events

-analyze the structure and meaning of individual parts of the text, taking into account differences in the structures of the native and studied languages. translate individual text fragments.

- establish a cause-and-effect relationship between facts and events in the text.

-evaluate the information received.

-comment on some facts/events of the text, expressing your opinion about what you read..

-evaluate the information received.

Reading with selective understanding of necessary or interesting information (scanning/search reading) involves the ability to look through a text or several short texts and select the necessary information of interest to students for further use in the process of communication or expanding knowledge on the problem of the text/texts.

In the process of mastering these types of reading, strategies should be used to form the following skills:

- determine the topic, the main content of the text by the title, selective reading of text fragments;
- highlight semantic milestones, the main idea of the text;
- select the main facts from the text, omitting the secondary ones;
- establish a logical sequence of the main facts of the text;
- identify cause-and-effect relationships in the text;

When increasing the reading competence of students through independent work, two principles help. The principle of informativeness is linked to the categories of professional significance and novelty. Since a text is, first of all, a communicative unit that is chosen by the reader for a specific purpose, it is important to include in the educational process texts that are interesting from a communicative point of view, that is, they present new, professionally significant information for students. The principle of authenticity involves selecting texts from original sources, while the principle of terminological richness involves selecting texts with a high content of terms. If authenticity actualizes the logical complexity of the text as its objective property, then terminological richness actualizes its semantic complexity. These two principles are necessary in the selection of material for modern reading activities of students, since they contribute to the formation of reader independence and a culture of independent work necessary in the professional activity of a specialist in any field.

Thus, the selection of texts according to the presented principles determines the content of the discipline and is used to develop a set of educational materials. The effective organization of the complex is facilitated by the modular construction of updated content. Educational, training, assessment and reinforcement modules involve varying degrees of representation of educational texts: from pre-selected by the teacher to independently selected by students. Modularity in the process of developing a student's reading competence allows for a gradual transition to awareness of one's own reading needs, to the development and practical application of ways to satisfy them within the framework of independently selected text material.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, as a result of the study of psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature, a contradiction was identified between the need to develop a high level of reading competence in students, allowing them to effectively carry out educational and future professional activities, and the lack of theoretical justification and scientific and methodological support for the process of developing reading skills.

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